

Spoken learner language via videomediated communication: a multimodal corpus pragmatics approach

Gerard O' Hanlon (Mary Immaculate College, Limerick, Ireland)

Video-mediated communication – commonplace in professional and social settings – also permits multimodal affordances in pedagogical contexts. All communication is multimodal (Jewitt et al., 2016) be it face-to-face or distant, spoken or written, synchronous or asynchronous (Adami, 2017). This involves modes such as gaze, gesture and nods combining to orchestrate (online) communicative events. Therefore, to fully understand language acquisition, it is necessary to investigate multimodality (Urbanski and Stam, 2022).

Most corpora are monomodal (i.e. transcribed/written data) (Knight & Adolphs, 2020). Multimodal corpora (i.e. the employment of additional layers of annotated metadata, e.g. gestures) are gaining traction thanks to technological advances (Chanier & Lamy, 2017). Thus, a video-mediated repository of spoken learner interaction will add greatly to learner corpus research.

Annotation is common to both multimodality and corpus pragmatics. It is held that pragmatics should be further incorporated into language learning pedagogy (Bardovi-Harlig, 2017). This PhD project therefore aims to highlight pragmatic features in spoken learner interactions using a multimodal corpus approach.

I address the following questions:

-How do English language learners perform request sequences in pairs during spoken video-mediated interactions?

-What role does multimodality play in the competence and performance of these L2 pragmatic interactions?

This research gathers a video-mediated dataset via Zoom and analyses it using AntConc and ELAN. Four adult English language learners at B2 level participated in the initial study. Open roleplays were used to elicit spoken request sequences. The data were transcribed and manually annotated for spoken pragmatic and embodied features of requests (i.e. gesture, head, face, gaze) in ELAN.

Preliminary results show that English language learners employ multimodal potentialities in online dyadic video-mediated interactions to augment requests, including paralanguage (e.g. pauses, loudness, rapid speech), gesture (literal, deictic, stress and non-literal movements),

gaze patterns related to politeness and imposition, and facial expressions signalling dispreferred responses. Findings from this research have potential applications in the fields of EAP and teacher training, for example.

References

Adami, E. (2016) 'Multimodality' in Garcia, O., Flores, N. and Spotti, M., eds., *Oxford Handbook of Language and Society*, Oxford: Oxford University Press, 451–472

Bardovi-Harlig (2017) 'Acquisition of L2 Pragmatics' in Loewen, S. and Sato, M., eds., *The Routledge Handbook of Instructed Second Language Acquisition*, London and New York: Routledge, 224-245

Chanier, T. and Lamy, M. (2017) *Researching Technology-mediated Multimodal Interaction*, in Chapelle, C.A. and Sauro, S. (eds), *The Handbook of Technology and Second Language Teaching and Learning*, Oxford: Wiley Blackwell 428-443

Jewitt, C., Bezemer, J. and O'Halloran, K. (2016) *Introducing Multimodality*, London: Routledge

Knight, D. and Adolphs, S. (2020) 'Multimodal Corpora' in Paquot, M. and Gries, S.Th., eds., *A Practical Handbook of Corpus Linguistics*. Cham: Springer International Publishing, 353-371

Urbanski, K. and Stam, G. (2022) 'Overview of multimodality and gesture in second language acquisition', in Stam, G. and Urbanski, K. eds., *Gesture and Multimodality in Second Language Acquisition, A Research Guide*. London: Routledge. 1-25